

Effects of Mindfulness-Based Interventions on Fear of Childbirth and Pain intensity management during Labour: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis

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ABSTRACT

Background: The efficacy of mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) in addressing labour pain and fear of childbirth (FOC) stands as an important area of inquiry. This systematic review and meta-analysis seek to assess the impact of MBIs on labour pain and FOC through a comprehensive synthesis and analysis of current evidence.

Methods: Following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, a thorough literature search was conducted. Thirteen randomised controlled trials with a total of 924 mothers were selected for analysis. The primary outcomes assessed were labour pain intensity and fear of childbirth (FOC). These were measured using validated instruments such as Visual Analogue Scale and the Wijma Delivery Expectancy Questionnaire.

Results: The results demonstrated significant decreases in fear of childbirth (FOC), (SMD = -0.93, 95% CI: -1.42 to -0.44; P<0.00001). and labour pain intensity (SMD = -1.12, 95% CI: -1.66 to -0.58; P<0.00001) among intervention groups. However, notable heterogeneity, variances in outcome measurement timepoints and participant features, alongside probable risk of bias stemming from study design constraints, necessitate judicious interpretation of these findings. While promising, the current evidence warrants further high-quality research to substantiate the efficacy of mindfulness-based interventions for FOC and labour pain.

Conclusions: Despite the limitations, MBIs present a promising non-pharmacological approach for managing FOC and labour pain. Future research should aim to mitigate methodological flaws present in current studies while striving to confirm these promising results. Implementation of MBIs into maternity care could offer a holistic approach, improving maternal and newborn outcomes.

Key words: Mindfulness-based interventions, Fear of Childbirth, Systematic review, Meta-analysis, Maternity care practices, Non-pharmacologic interventions, women's Health, Wijma Delivery Expectancy Questionnaire (W-DEQ), Visual analogues Scale (VAS)

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